

A REVIEW PAPER ON FREE VIBRATION ANALYSIS OF CRACKED R.C.C BEAM EXPERIMENTALLY

HARSHA U. ZURANGE

(Post graduate. Student Civil structure, JSPM, ICOER, Pune, India.)

PROF. SHUBHANGI A. KAKDE

(Assistant professor, Civil- structure, JSPM, ICOER, Pune, India.)

ABSTRACT:

In the present era, health of the structure is of great concern to avoid further hazards caused by deterioration of the structure. So due importance should be given to health aspect of a structure because health defines the long term performance of the structure. Health monitoring is the detection of the overall health of a structure, which includes cracking, spalling of concrete and anything which disturbs the utility of the structure. Many researchers are engaged in detection of cracks with the help of vibration analysis. This method of detection of cracks has been considered as an cost effective and reliable method of health monitoring. The effect of crack location and depth of crack on the natural frequencies and mode shapes has been reviewed in this paper.

The type of crack, its location and depth are the main governing parameters in this study and result parameters are mode shapes and frequencies. The experiment will be performed on test beams by using fast forrier analyser, accelerometer and hammer. Validation of experimental results will be done by ANSYS.

KEYWORDS: Cracks, Free vibration, Frequencies, Mode shapes, ANSYS.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Cracks are the most neglected type of damage that is caused to the structure. Many a times in our day to day life we neglect the existence of the cracks in our structure. But as a prominent civil engineer any crack however small may be can cause serious damage to the structure so it should not be neglected. These cracks disturbs the utility and life span of the structure. Cracks develop from flaws due to components like beams, columns, etc will bear damage due to its long term use. Hence it becomes important to determine the damage characteristics on the structures. Cracks causes changes in the physical properties of a structure which eventually alters its dynamic response characteristics. To detect these cracks inexpensive methods should be found out. Vibration analysis is one of those method in which researchers are focusing on the changes of modal parameters like natural frequencies, mode shapes and modal damping values. The health of the structure

should be monitored in a economical way. Using vibration technique researchers are analyzing its reliability and cost effectiveness. Due importance should be given to crack depth, its location, type and the effects caused by it on the health of the structure. Type of the crack also plays an important role in this study, as whether the crack is breathing crack or closed crack. Location of the crack means whether the crack is near the supports, edges or in the middle of the beam. Any damage however small may be alters the dynamic response of the structure causing stiffness reduction eventually resulting into changes in the natural frequencies and mode shapes of the structure. In this paper, the research done by previous researchers has been studied, viewed and analysed. Thus, modeling and the dynamics of the cracked structures has been a subject of intensive investigations in the last three decades.

1.1 LITERATURE REVIEW:

Here are some research reviews done by researchers Prathmesh1 In this paper a model for free vibration analysis of a beam with an open edge crack has been presented. Variations of natural frequencies due to crack at various locations and with varying crack depths have been studied. The cracked beams with different boundary conditions have been analyzed. The results obtained by experiments performed by previous studies are compared with those obtained by finite element analysis by using ABAQUS software. It was observed that the natural frequency changes substantially due to the presence of cracks depending upon location and size of crack.

Saidiabelkrim.et.al (2014)- He analyzed the vibration behavior of concrete beams both experimentally and using ANSYS software subjected to the crack under free vibration cases. Experiments were conducted by using FFT Analyzer, Accelerometer, Modal hammer. It was observed that when the location of the crack increases starting from the clamped end of the beam, natural frequencies of the beam and the amplitude of high frequency vibration also increase, but the amplitude of low frequency vibration decreases.

Sirca.et.al(2012)- presented system identification in structures using multi-paradigm approach for large

structures with non linear behavior subjected to unknown dynamic loading such as strong ground motions.

Huszar.et.al- studied the dynamic behavior of cracked reinforced and prestressed concrete beams using eigen frequencies. The connection between the prestressing force and the virtual eigen frequencies of the cracked beam was investigated by numeric simulation.

Kilichi.et.al(2004)- In this study, a technique of analyzing the vibration problem of reinforced concrete beam members including bond slip of the reinforcements is proposed. Virtual work is used to derive equations based on finite element method and numerical examples are provided.

Jena.et.al- presented theoretical, numerical (FEM) and experimental analysis of composite cracked beams of different boundary conditions using vibration mode shape curvatures. The effect on natural frequencies and mode shapes for different boundary conditions are studied by varying crack positions and crack depth. It has been concluded from this study that with increase in crack depth, the relative frequencies reduce in order due to drop in stiffness of the composite beam. It is also observed that the relative crack position affects the relative frequency of the composite beam.

Swapnil.et.al(2015)- carried out an experimental study on cracked cantilever beam using FFT analyzer. Accelerometer, Impact hammer and comparison of results using ANSYS. He concluded that natural frequency of the cracked beam increases as the crack location increases from fixed end and the crack depth is constant. Also small crack depth ratios had small effect on the sensitivity of the natural frequencies. It was also observed that the changes become more significant as the crack depth grew deeper.

Gurel.et.al(2007)- presented free vibration analysis of uniform and stepped cracked beams with circular cross sections. This theory uses flexibility matrices taking into account the interaction forces derived by virtue of fracture mechanics theory as the inverse of the compliance matrix found with the appropriate stress intensity factors and strain energy release rate expressions.

Yogeshshinde.et.al(2014)- In this paper vibrational analysis of cantilever beam with single open transverse crack for different crack depth and different crack locations is done using experimental method considering two cases i.e. without loading and with transverse loading and find out natural frequency of the beam.

Reismurat.et.al(2010)-In this paper investigation of the vibration of a cracked cantilever beam under moving mass load. The existence of crack induces a local flexibility which is a function of the crack depth, thereby changing its vibrational behaviour and the eigen values of the system.

The response of the system is obtained in terms of Duhamel integral.

O. Giannini.et.al(2013):The paper proposes a methodology for the identification of breathing cracks in beams able to detect simultaneously the location and the depth of the damage. The presence of such a damage generates, even for small severity of the crack, nonlinear features in the response of the structure. The proposed method uses a set of tests, each exciting one mode and, by combining the obtained information, a sharp identification is achieved through a minimization problem. The concept of modal-effective damage is introduced because each mode is sensitive to the location of the damage in its individual way and this is relevant on a two-fold point of view.

Lankaramesh.et.al(2016): The main focus on this paper is to form a relationship between the modal natural frequencies for the different crack depth for that vibration analysis is carried out on a cantilever beam with two open transverse cracks on universal vibration apparatus. Modelling and simulation is done by finite element analysis software package ANSYS. It has been found that when natural frequencies increase and mode shape decrease as the crack depth increases.

Dayalparhi.et.al(2012): He analysed two transverse cracks from fixed end of the beam, by experimentally and by using finite element analysis ANSYS. The depth of the cracks are varied from 0.5mm to 3mm at the interval of 0.5mm. It has been found that natural frequencies increase and mode shapes decrease as the crack depth increases.

2. OBJECTIVES:

- 1)To carry out vibration analysis experimentally on R.C.C beams.
- 2)To study behaviour on natural frequencies of cracks at varying locations and depth.
- 3)To compare the results of frequencies and mode shapes by experiment and software.
- 4)To compare results of intact beam & corresponding cracked beam.

3. METHODOLOGY:

The methodology includes vibrational analysis of cracked r.c.c beam experimentally by varying the crack location and depth of crack. Parameters studied will be natural frequencies and mode shapes. Validation of the results by software.

4. TECHNICAL DETAILS OF THE PROJECT:

Beam Size: 150*150*600mm

Mix Proportion: M20(1:1.5:3)

Crack location: 100mm from support

Crack depth: 0.5mm, 1mm, 1.5mm,2mm, 2.5mm, 3mm

Clear cover for beams: 20mm

Support Condition 1) Both end fixed.

Location of crack: 100mm from fixed end.

6 beams for support conditions will be casted by varying the crack depths as 0.5mm, 1mm, 1.5mm, 2mm, 2.5mm, 3mm analyzed.

The major parameters studied under vibration analysis are modal frequencies and mode shapes of those of the cracked beams and intact beams.

5. FIELD APPLICATIONS:

This topic finds many applications in the fields of civil and mechanical engineering structures.

1. Vibration analysis is used for early detection of faults in structural components.
2. The use of vibration for finding out natural frequency, mode shaped of the cracked beam is found to be cost effective and accurate method. Hence can be used for structural health monitoring of different components.
3. The dynamic behavior of different structural components can be studied.
4. Vibration analysis is also used to detect faults in rotating equipment and machineries like pumps, electric motors, internal combustion engines etc.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Many researchers have modeled the crack as a mass less torsional linear spring, assuming that its constant stiffness is related to the mechanical properties of the beam.

Natural frequency is reduced because of the local flexibility reduces the stiffness of a structural component. It can be concluded that presence of crack changes the natural frequency of the structural component.

There is extensive confusion in the literature in distinguishing between a notch and a crack. Many authors treat cracks as notches, experimentally, analytically or numerically. Saw cuts are used to model cracks. It must be understood that no matter how thin a saw cut is, it will not behave as a crack.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I express my deepest gratitude to my project guide Prof. Shubhangi Kakde whose encouragement, guidance and support me to develop an understanding of the subject.

Dr. A.W.Dhawale Head of the Civil Engineering Department, JSPM, ICOER for providing their invaluable advice and giving opportunities to do this project successfully.

Finally, I take this opportunity to extend my deep appreciation to my family and friends, for all that they meant to me during the crucial times of my project.

REFERENCES:

- 1) P M Jagdale.et.al "*Free Vibration Analysis of Cracked Beam* International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications ISSN: 2248-9622 Volume 3 (1172-1176).
- 2) Saidi abdelkrim et al "*Experimental Test for the Detection of Damage to a Concrete Beam* International Conference on Geological and Civil Engineering IPCBEE Volume 62.
- 3) Sirca et al "*System Identification in structural engineering* Scientia Iranica A(2012) 19 (6), 1355-1364.
- 4) Huszar et al "*Vibrations of cracked reinforced and Prestressed Concrete Beams*" Architecture and Civil Engineering Vol 6,155-164.
- 5) Keiichi et al "*Vibration Analysis of reinforced concrete beam members including bond slip of reinforcement*" 13th world conference on Earth quake engineering paper number 604.
- 6) P.K Jena et al "*Effect of damage parameters on vibration signatures of a cantilever beam*" International Conference on Modeling, Optimization and Computing April 10-11-2012 Procedia Engineering 38 (2012) 3318 – 3330
- 7) Swapnil.et.al "*Effects of Crack on Modal Frequency of Cantilever Beam*" International Journal of Research in Aeronautical and Mechanical Engineering Vol 3 pg 24-38.
- 8) Gurel.et.al "*Free vibration analysis of uniform and stepped cracked beams with circular cross sections* International Journal of Engineering Science 364-380.
- 9) Yogesh.et.al "*Vibration analysis of cantilever beam with single crack using experimental method* International journal of Engineering Research and Technology Volume 3.
- 10) *A textbook of Structural Dynamics* by Mario Paz.
- 11) *Indian Standard code of practice 456:2000* as and when needed.